

Emerging Media: collecting, preservation and access challenges

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British Library and the Legal Deposit

Libraries Committee

1. Introduction
2. Case study - Interactive Documentary
3. Case study - Interactive Narrative
4. Panel discussion
5. Next steps

Introduction

The background is huge **economic** growth and substantial **public funding** to incubate, innovate, train, develop audience engagement and creative capacity

1. Economic growth predictions – search ‘**Immerse UK report**’

- \$1 billion in revenue in 2018
- \$95 billion in 2025 (Goldman Sachs)
- \$108 billion in 2021 (TechCrunch)
- \$569 billion in 2025 (Citi)

2. Major UK government funding programme - search ‘**UKRI Audience of the Future**’

- Industry Centre of Excellence (ICE) in Immersive Storytelling
- Demonstrator programme for immersive innovation

A FESTIVAL APPROACH TO PRESERVING EMERGING & INTERACTIVE STORYTELLING FEATS

erwin verbruggen

netherlands institute for sound and vision

SOUND AND VISION

SOUND AND VISION

WEBARCHIEF
OMROEPEN

BEELD EN GELUID

Zoeken...

PREMtime
NOVA
SPANGAS
VERRE VERWANTEN

MELD EEN WEBSITE AAN

BEELD EN GELUID BLOG

14/09/2010
ILLUSTRATIES VAN HANS DE COCK IN
BEELD EN GELUID
09/07/2010
DE CLAMMUS KICK-OFF
08/01/2010
8 APRIL: SPANJE TIPS EVENT BIJ BEELD EN
GELUID
19/02/2010
KRONIEK VAN EEN AANREKENDING
ELFSTREKTOETS

HET WEBARCHIEF BEVAT

5

WEERDIELEN, MET TOTAAL
303.618
BEELDEN
SINCE 30 OKTOBER 2011

PREMtime

Oorspronkelijke url: <http://premtime.nl/nieuws/48/>
Let op: je hebt een geschiedenis versie van deze website.
Mogelijk werken zoekbalk, formulieren en externe links niet naar behoren.

22 MAR 2013

PREMtime

Dagelijks gaat Prem met de Blue Bird Vision het land in. Op weg naar het nieuws, op zoek naar de bron.
Elke werkdag van 10:30 tot 11:00 | Radio 1

home | nieuws | afleveringen | de bus | over prem | colofon | contact | column | Zoeken

NIEUWS

LIJN 1: vanaf 14 september
Prem neemt afscheid (Den Haag)
Jeanine Henis-Plasschaert, VVD
(Hilversum)
Martijn van Helvert, CDA
(Hilversum)
Renske Leijten, SP (Hilversum)

PREMtime: BORSTVOEDING (EDE)

(Foto: Flickr/Elas)
Vandaag staat PREMtime bij het **Borstvoedingscongres** in congrescentrum De Reehorst in Ede, waar de crème de la crème van borstvoedend

VOLG ONS!

PREMtime GEMIST?

Bekijk [hier](#) het complete archief.

@PREMtimeRADIO1

Shajstareve
#FollowBack #FF #SV
Premtime 16 pazzakonta
nê Maqedon, nuse për
beçarët dhe ekskursionë ...
<http://t.co/675uYKf8e>
#TeamFollowBack #TFB

SOUND AND VISION

U bevindt zich hier: [Home](#) > [Zoeken](#) > Beeld en Geluid catalogus

ZOEKEN IN BEELD EN GELUID CATALOGUS

◀ Zoekresultaten [Opnieuw zoeken](#)

[Alle klassen](#) | [Alle uitklassen](#) | [Print](#)

◀ Resultaat 2 van 2 ▶

INTERNETVIDEO

Zendgemachtigde
Uitzenddatum

NIET VAN TOEPASSING ;
09-01-2015;

Titel
Aanleveringstitel
Publicaties

INTERNETVIDEO
Amin Mousaoui #JesuisAhmed
internet; 09-01-2015; NIET VAN TOEPASSING; 1' 57"

Schone inlas
Dragers

Niet aanwezig
Geen dragers beschikbaar

Samenvatting

De Rotterdamse Amin Mousaoui valt in dit filmpje uit tegen de extremisten die in Parijs (Frankrijk) een bloedige aanslag hebben gepleegd op de redactie van het satirische tijdschrift Charlie Hebdo. In zijn betoog zegt hij onder meer: "Ik accepteer niet dat bepaalde extremistische hufters telkens mijn religie als godium misbruiken". Hij pleit voor verbroedering: "schouder aan schouder, ongeacht de god waar je in gelooft". Mousaoui plaatste zijn betoog op Facebook, waar het massaal is gedeeld.

Genre
Trefwoorden
Geografische namen
Beoogd medium
Rechten
Task ID

internetvideo - acties
Aanslagen ; extremisme ; moslims
Frankrijk ; Parijs
internet
Herkomst YouTube
5172889
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=81ob6-s7V28>

SOUND AND VISION

BEELD EN GELUID

GAMESCANON

JAZZ JACKRABBIT

jaar: 1994 ontwikkelaar: Epic Megagames platform: DOS

Jazz Jackrabbit is een computerspel voor de pc uit 1994, geproduceerd door Epic MegaGames. Het spel is geschreven in Turbo Pascal 7.0 door de Nederlandse programmeur Arjan Brussee en bedacht door Cliff Bleszinski. Het spel was zo populair dat er in 1998 een vervolg, Jazz Jackrabbit 2, werd gemaakt.

Van het spel bestaan verschillende versies. Allereerst was er de sharewareversie die bestond uit één aflevering. Een aflevering bestond uit drie werelden, elk onderverdeeld in twee levels en een 3D-bonuslevel. Verder zat er in iedere aflevering nog één geheim level dat bereikt kon worden door te schieten op een rood bord met een geel vraagteken. De aflevering eindigt met een Guardian

Julie herinneringen

+ VOEG JOUW HERINNERING TOE!

XXL-clan rulez!

XXL-XXL • Gisteren 21:33

WE SPEAK A NEW AND
POWERFUL LANGUAGE,
CAPABLE OF SAYING THINGS
NO OTHER LANGUAGE CAN
SAY, BUT FEW HAVE REALIZED
THIS, AND EVEN FEWER HAVE
FOUND WHAT TO SAY.

Jonathan Harris

MAIN INGREDIENTS

STORY

INTERACTION

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY

CAPTURED REALITY

ONFB

idfa
DOCLAB

TFI
NEW MEDIA
FUND

submarine
channel

POWER
TO THE
PIXEL

MIT OPEN
DOCUMENTARY
LAB

Sheffield
Doc/Fest

BBC iD

france télévisions

POV

Future of
StoryTelling

Sundance Film Festival

WORLD PRESS PHOTO

theguardian
quality independent journalism

CROSS
VIDEO DAYS

Dpt.

the
creators
project

BuzzFeed

klynt

arte

idfa DOCLAB IMMERSIVE NETWORK

Made possible by

Ministry of Economic Affairs of the
Netherlands

Supported by

arte

SOUND AND VISION

Past events

DocLab Live: Bloodless –
Guided by the Ghost of a
Korean Sex Worker

Hieronymus Bosch, The Eyes of the Owl

**An innovative way to experience Bosch's most
famous painting up close and personal.**

Hieronymus Bosch, The Eyes of the Owl is a virtual reality

[Project details](#)

**I'M NOT
HOME
VIDEO**

BY BERT HANA

Past events

**DocLab Live: Bloodless –
Guided by the Ghost of a
Korean Sex Worker**
25 Nov 2017 at 17:00

Bear 71 VR

WATCH PROJECT

A seminal piece in the history of interactive documentary, reimagined and re-released as a virtual reality experience.

Bear 71 is a groundbreaking interactive documentary experience, told from the point of view of Bear 71, a female grizzly bear living in

Project details

Year of development : 2016

Past events

**DocLab Live: Bloodless –
Guided by the Ghost of a
Korean Sex Worker**
25 Nov 2017 at 17:00

Clickclickclick.click

In a likeable, playful clickbait experience, you are rewarded for exploring all the interactive possibilities of your mouse.

You and your mouse – an intimate relationship you seldom really think about. But your mouse behavior can betray as much of your identity as your search terms. With Clickclickclick.click Studio

Project details

Year of development : 2016
Created by: Luna Maurer, Roel Wouters

Past events

DocLab Live: Bloodless – Guided by the Ghost of a Korean Sex Worker
25 Nov 2017 at 17:00

Special presentation on VR installation *Bloodless*, in which director Gisa Kim and

Refugee Republic

WATCH PROJECT

You think refugees are passive victims? Then spend some time in Domiz in northern Iraq and find out what everyday life in a camp is really like.

People desperately or resignedly waiting for help in the heat and the dust – this is the image most of us associate with refugee

Project details

Year of development : 2014

Created by Dirk Jan Vinger, Jan

AGGING

CAMP CONSTRUCTION ROUTE

to open this kitchen set you need the knife (inside this box)

'On his way to the bakers my husband was arrested'

Firas reopened his building materials store in no-man's-land.

We fled because the safety of our

Camp Facts

used for receiving new arrivals, with the exception of family reunification. The camp is located 20 kms southeast of Dohuk city, in Iraqi Kurdistan and 60 km from Syria-Iraq border. The size of Domiz Camp is 1,142,500 m².

Preserving Interactives

White Paper

May 2018

Author

Erwin Verbruggen
Sound and Vision

Server-side Preservation of Dynamic Websites

White Paper

July 2018

Prepared by Rasa Bočytė
University Supervisor Annet Dekker (UvA)
Internship Supervisors Erwin Verbruggen, Jesse de Vos (Sound and Vision)

<http://publications.beeldengeluid.nl>

Breathe

A Ghost Story by Kate Pullinger

Caylin Smith, Legal Deposit Libraries Senior Project Manager

No Time to Wait, BFI, London, October 25th 2018

Outline

- Context

- UK Non-Print Legal Deposit
- Emerging Formats project

- About *Breathe*

- <https://breathe-story.com/>

- Capturing *Breathe* using web archiving tools

- Heritrix
- Webrecorder

UK Non-Print Legal Deposit

- Legal Deposit has existed in the UK in some form since 1662
- The Legal Deposit Libraries Act 2003
 - 1 copy of a publication sent to the British Library and any of the other libraries that claim it
- The Legal Deposit Libraries (Non-Print Works) Regulations 2013
 - Allowed the libraries to collect publications created in digital formats
 - Publishers must deposit a digital file that is suitable for long-term preservation
- Currently collect eBooks (EPUB and PDF), eJournals (PDF), maps (raster and vector formats), notated music (PDF), and the UK web domain (WARC)
- Preserved within the British Library's digital repository
- Access provided onsite on designated desktop terminals at each LDL

Emerging Formats project

- Two year project (April 2017 – present)
- Identifying publications that are in scope to collect under legal deposit
- Exploring the collection management needs of more-complex digital publications
- Focused on three types of content
 - eBook mobile apps (e.g. academic books, dictionaries, children's literature)
 - Web-based interactive narratives (e.g. narrative games, ambient literature, literature written for platforms like Twine)
 - Structured data (e.g. statistics, official reports)

About *Breathe*

- Created by Kate Pullinger in collaboration with Editions at Play (Visual Editions + Google's Creative Lab)
- Read time 15-20 minutes; 105 pages in total
- Browser-based work of ambient fiction written in HTML that is best viewed on mobile devices
- Reader progresses the narrative by swiping left on their mobile device, or touching icon in bottom right corner
- Uses APIs to personalise the narrative to the reader's surroundings
 - Use of device's camera, GPS, and weather data
 - a "book that comes to you"

Observations

- Mainly textual, but does include some images
 - Use of device's camera to create background imagery
- Different types of interaction (e.g. tilting the screen) are required to reveal the full story
 - The narrative does not always appear immediately onscreen
- Behavior is impacted by type of device (mobile phone, tablet), operating system (iOS, Android), browser

Breathe as displayed in Chrome

Breathe as displayed in Safari

Capturing *Breathe*

- Heritrix
- Web Recorder

Heritrix

Targets > Breathe: A Ghost Story by Kate Pullinger

View Edit

Overview Metadata Crawl policy and Schedule NPLD scope (+) UKWA Licencing (-)

Watched Target

Title	Breathe: A Ghost Story by Kate Pullinger
Seed URL(s) (One or more URLs, separated by commas, including the http://)	https://breathe-story.com/
Aliases/Synonyms (If this content is also hosted at another URL, record it here. For example, if www.company.co.uk is the same as www.company.com)	
Record creation date	22-02-2018
Record last update	13-09-2018 10:01
Owned by	Nicola Bingham
QA Status	none
Live Site Status (If known, please add the current status of the site)	Still live
Hidden (Is this target hidden from public)	no
Key Site (Is this a 'key site', i.e. one of such significance that it requires higher levels of QA and archival management)	no
WCT ID	
SPT ID	
Keywords (Free text keywords, private to you)	

Instances

<https://breathe-story.com/>

- Search QA Wayback
- Search Open UK Web Archive
- Search Other Web Archives

Crawl Logs

<https://breathe-story.com/>

- Find URL in crawl logs
- Find all URLs with this prefix in the crawl logs

Screen capture of *Breathe* within the BL's Annotation Curation Tool, an open source, selective web archiving workflow management application

You are here: [Home](#) > Open UK Web Archive

Provided by:

Enter Web Address:

Searched for <https://breathe-story.com/> Set Anchor Window: none 0 Results

Search Results for 1 Jan, 1996 - 31 Dec, 2018

Jan 1996	Jan 1998	Jan 2000	Jan 2002	Jan 2004	Jan 2006	Jan 2008	Jan 2010	Jan 2012	Jan 2014	Jan 2016	Jan 2018 -	14 pages
- Dec 1997	- Dec 1999	- Dec 2001	- Dec 2003	- Dec 2005	- Dec 2007	- Dec 2009	- Dec 2011	- Dec 2013	- Dec 2015	- Dec 2017		
0 pages	0 pages											

- [23 Feb, 2018](#) *
- [24 Feb, 2018](#) *
- [25 Feb, 2018](#) *
- [26 Feb, 2018](#) *
- [27 Feb, 2018](#) *
- [28 Feb, 2018](#) *
- [1 Mar, 2018](#) *
- [13 Sep, 2018](#) *
- [14 Sep, 2018](#) *
- [15 Sep, 2018](#) *
- [16 Sep, 2018](#) *
- [17 Sep, 2018](#) *
- [18 Sep, 2018](#) *
- [19 Sep, 2018](#) *

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Screen capture of the UK Web Archive showing the amount of crawls for *Breathe*

UK WA External links, forms and search boxes may not function within this archived website.

<https://breathe-story.com/> Go «MAR SEP OCT

Show all captures 23 Feb 18 - 19 Sep 18

2017 19 2018 2019

Close ×
Cymraeg
Help ?

Screen capture of *Breathe* as displayed in the UK Web Archive

Webrecorder

Screen capture of *Breathe* (cover page) in Chrome DevTools on Linux desktop computer

Screen capture of *Breathe* (cover page) within Chrome (v60) within Webrecorder Player

Webrecorder / emerging_formats / interactive narratives Submit a bug My Collections (2) emerging_formats

Chrome v60 | https://breathe-story.com/ 19/06/2018, 08:05:59

Breathe - The book | x

Secure | https://breathe-story.com/book

Breathe

1 / 105

Elements Console Sources Network Performance

html body #root div div div div inner [App_loading-steam_IX9YX]

Styles Event Listeners DOM Breakpoints Properties

```
element.style {
}
.app_loading-steam_IX9YX {
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  right: 0;
  bottom: 0;
}
```

Console What's New

- Failed to load resource: the server responded with a status of 404 (Not Found) collect
- Failed to load resource: the server responded with a status of 404 (Not Found) default-user-media-fc6e83b...
- Failed to load resource: the server responded with a status of 404 (Not Found) /get-pages
- POST https://breathe-story.com/get-pages 404 (Not Found) get-pages:1
- GET https://breathe-story.com/static/default-user-media-fc6e83b...ip:1 404 (Not Found)
- GET https://www.google-analytics.com/r/collect?v=1&v=1685a-1996 collect:1 392844t-pagew-3195781t-id=1A-78164796-78_gid=1564658356_15293919596_r-160ta-1646-98892376 404 (Not Found)
- Access to Font at 'https://fonts.gstatic.com/s/averlaserifibrev/y/n/book1e1bD2m4wxr6Gvie00X88HPyX2y0p2Mw58xY.woff2' from origin 'https://breathe-story.com' has been blocked by CORS policy: No 'Access-Control-Allow-Origin' header is present on the requested resource. Origin 'https://breathe-story.com' is therefore not allowed access. The response had HTTP status code 404.

Screen capture of *Breathe* (page 1) within Chrome (v60) within Webrecorder Player

Next steps

- Identify URLs of individual pages to crawl with Heritrix
 - Engage with Editions at Play to better understand how *Breathe* was created
- Engage with Webrecorder community to see whether and how the text of the narrative can be captured

Thank you!

@caylinssmith, #uknpId

caylin.smith@bl.uk

emerging-formats@bl.uk

Acknowledgements: Nicola Bingham, Ian Cooke, Maureen Pennock,
and Adam Leggott

Panel discussion

- Learning from previous experiences
- Creating a body of knowledge - with case studies
- Organising events to accrue knowledge, form networks
- Working with creators and industry, including tech companies
- Standards and standardisation:
 - how soon is too soon for standards?
 - opportunities for open source advocacy?
 - what is our role as preservation professionals?
- System suppliers and service suppliers
- Emulators and emulation for operating systems etc
- Leveraging developer tools for digipres outcomes

Next steps

- Organise **events** to build knowledge and form networks
- Create **working groups** to co-ordinate activities in the networks
- Create **forums** for discussion by the networks - Slack workspaces / channels?
- Invite **industry / makers** to present their work / expertise
- Talk to creators about **preservation** - explain our work to them, in clear language

Don't miss: 9 March 2019, CSM London - Vanishing Point: The Curation and Preservation of Virtual Reality

http://bit.ly/VanishingPoint_CSM